

PROBONO

Quality Plan and Monitoring (I)

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PST	Project Steering Team
PO	Project Officer
Q(A)M	Quality (Assurance) Management
TCC	Technical Coordination Committee
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive summary

This document defines the quality assurance procedures that each partner should take into consideration within the PROBONO project. The primary intention is to provide the project participants with a practical handbook describing the quality criteria, controls, and corrective mechanisms for the Project's Quality Assurance.

These procedures provide a mechanism not only for reviewing Deliverables but also for ensuring that corrective actions are taken where necessary, in order to provide high-quality Deliverables.

This Deliverable is related to the WP10 of PROBONO and is the formal Deliverable D10.6 "Quality Plan and Monitoring (I)" submitted on M12 of the project (December 2022). It is important to mention that this is the first Deliverable in a series of five (one per annum), and D10.10 "Quality Plan and Monitoring (FINAL)" will be the final one at M60 (December 2026). This first deliverable presents the guidelines for quality, while in the final version the results of the implementation of QAM will be reported.

This report is also associated with a list of internal templates that PROBONO has produced in order to facilitate the project's smooth execution, as well as, to ensure the achievement of high-quality levels for the project as whole.

1 Introduction

This document is related to Task 10.3: Quality Assurance and defines the quality assurance procedures followed within the PROBONO project.

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map PROBONO's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and the Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 10.3 - Quality Assurance	<p><u>Quality Assurance</u></p> <p>This task will clearly specify the quality procedures, internal and external peer reviews, and will monitor reporting activities to ensure that satisfactory quality standards are met.</p> <p>Quality Plan and Quality Procedures: Implementation of a quality plan, templates and procedures for quality management and reporting; defining quality standards for reports, quality reviews, peer reviews, control, deliverables, software tools, monitoring and reporting activities and related templates.</p> <p>Quality Monitoring and Control: Monitoring quality to ensure that project deliverables (reports, software, demonstration scenarios etc.) meet the defined quality standards and conform with security requirements.</p>	Chapter 2 and Annexes I-V	Quality assurance criteria and processes are described along with responsible people and information about Project workspace, file naming and formatting. Templates identified are also included in Annexes I-V, along with a list with the Peer Reviewers per Deliverable.
DELIVERABLE			
<p><u>D10.6: Quality Plan and Monitoring (I)</u></p> <p>Initial version of project's Quality Plan and Monitoring. This report formulates the findings of T10.3, and explores step A) Report to include the project quality control procedures and deliverable review templates.</p>			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Chapter 2 of the document describes the procedures for the quality management and reporting of PROBONO. It also provides templates that will be used in the reviewing process, a list of deadlines and a list of the peer reviewers allocated to each Deliverable. The aim of this Deliverable is to serve as a practical handbook for the project partners that defines the quality criteria, procedures, controls and corrective mechanisms for the Quality Assurance of the following:

- Report oriented Deliverables
- Reports of the software-oriented Demonstrators

These procedures provide a mechanism not only for reviewing Deliverables but also for ensuring that corrective actions will continuously be taken to drive improvements in the quality assurance procedures themselves. Annual quality reports will be produced summarizing the following results:

- Analysis of the outcomes of the review procedure
- Recommendations for improving the quality of Deliverables and quality assurance procedures during the next period.

The appropriate information regarding the measurements and evaluation criteria which will be used as a quality metric for reporting are also included in Annexes as listed below:

- Annex I: Peer Review Scoring Template;

- Annex II: Peer Reviewers per Deliverable for Year 1;
- Annex III: Deliverable Template;
- Annex IV: Presentation Template;
- Annex V: Telco/ Physical Meeting Minutes Template.

2 Quality Assurance

The purpose of the quality plan and procedures is to ensure that the Deliverables are of satisfactory level of quality in terms of both their content and presentation. Therefore, hereby we define that the Deliverables must be:

- Consistent with the description of work (DoW), in order to ensure that results are fully compliant with the Grant Agreement (GA).
- Consistent with the project plan, in order to ensure that results contribute to the overall project's objectives as defined by the project's coordination team.
- Clear and readable.

More information about the quality criteria and processes of the report-oriented Deliverables are described in Section 2.3, while in Section 2.4 the Guidelines for Software Oriented Deliverables Quality Procedures are described.

2.1 Roles and Responsibilities

Formally, as part of T10.3 (Quality Assurance), the quality of PROBONO's Deliverables is monitored throughout the project by the **Quality Manager** (eBOS) in collaboration with the **WP10 Leader** (Project Management) and **Project Coordinator** (ACC) as well as the **Technical Coordinator** (INLE).

The Technical Coordinator will help ensure the direction and coherence of the technical outputs,

- by getting involved in the conceptual stage of the critical technical deliverables (i.e., giving advice on the ToC);
- monitor progress of the respective work and offer recommendations during the monthly PST calls.
- For a few critical deliverables, to be identified by the end of this year, INLE will also be more actively involved in their review.

Nevertheless, the **authors** together with the **contributors**, the **WPL** and the **Peer Reviewers** of all Technical Deliverables are the ultimate owners of the responsibility to ensure that the technical output is at high-quality standards and adequately fulfils the project's contractual obligations.

The key contacts and roles are shown in Table 2 below.

Roles	Partner	Contact Person	Contact Email
Project Coordinator/WP10 Project Manager	ACC	Magdalena Rozanska	magdalena.rozanska@acciona.com
Quality Managers	EBOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Georgia Pantelide ▪ Philippos Philippou 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ georgiap@ebos.com.cy ▪ philipposp@ebos.com.cy
Technical Coordinator	INLE	Marina Laskari	marina.laskari@inlecomsystems.com
Work Package Leaders	Each WP Leader is identified in Description of Actions (DoA)		
Deliverable Owner/Author	Each Deliverable owner is identified in DoA		
Peer Reviewers	The peer reviewers per Deliverable are identified in Annex II of the existing Deliverable		

Table 2: Project Roles and Contacts

2.2 Resources, Files and General Procedures

2.2.1 Project Space

The project coordinator (ACC) has set up a shared space to facilitate information exchange and file sharing between project partners in Office 365 SharePoint. Office 365 SharePoint is an online tool, fully compliant with all the security and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1] requirements, that can be used by the partners as the primary location for uploading and storing files related to the PROBONO project, such as Deliverables, Meeting Minutes, Workshop Photos and other working documents as well as videos.

Particular access to Office 365 SharePoint has been arranged for all users of the tool (project partners). No users/persons outside the consortium have any access to this tool. The access rights are granted after communication with the project manager that also supervises this tool. To access Teams, the users need to follow the below link

<https://acciona365.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/PROBONO/Shared%20Documents/General?csf=1&web=1&e=vYM5LU>

which, after login (as shown in Figure 1), directly navigates them to the home page of Projects' Team Homepage (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Microsoft Teams login screen

Figure 2: Project Repository Homepage / Files

As shown in Figure 2, there is a specific file structure where each file should be uploaded and stored. All Work Packages (WP) have dedicated folders, where the relevant Telco information, minutes and Working Documents should be Uploaded. The Deliverables should be uploaded on the dedicated “Deliverables” folder under the WP respective subfolders. In addition, under the folder WP8 Communication, all the necessary template files (e.g., Deliverable Template, Presentation template, Meeting Minutes, etc) can be found and downloaded by the partners.

2.2.2 File Format and Naming

All the working and exchanged (between the partners) documents should be in a format that can be easily edited and/or amended. For that reason, it is preferable to use file types supported by Microsoft Office.

In order to have a unique way to identify the official project’s documents, a naming template has been defined as presented *Table 3* below, along with an example for each document type.

Document Type	Naming Template	Example
Deliverables	[PROBONO]-[DX.Y]- [Deliverable_Title]- [DDMMYY]-[Version]- [Beneficiary].docx	PROBONO-D10.6– <u>Quality_Plan_and_monitoring</u> – <u>300922</u> – v0.1-EBOS.docx Deliverable title with underscores Date format
Agendas	[PROBONO]-[Meeting ID]- [Meeting_Location(or Online)]-[Agenda]- [DDMMYY]-[Version]. Meeting’s identifiers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ KOM = Kick Off Meeting ▪ PST = Project Steering Team ▪ PM = Project Meeting (concerns regular General Assemblies) ▪ TM = Technical Meeting ▪ RM = Review Meeting ▪ Telco = Online meeting (Skype, GoToMeeting, WebEx, Teams, etc.) 	PROBONO-KOM-ONLINE-Agenda-080222-v1
Minutes following the organization of an online or physical meeting	[PROBONO]-[Meeting ID]- [Meeting_Location(or Online)]-[Minutes]- [DDMMYY]-[Version].	PROBONO-KOM-ONLINE-Minutes-080222-v1
Presentations	[PROBONO]-[WP]- [Meeting ID]- [Presentation_Title]- [DDMMYY]-[Beneficiary]	PROBONO_WP10_QA_Plan-100522-EBOS

Table 3: Documents Naming Conventions

In the Annexes, screenshots of the appropriate document templates are presented as listed below:

- **Annex I:** Peer Review Scoring Template
- **Annex III:** Deliverable Template;
- **Annex IV:** Presentation Template;
- **Annex V:** Telco/ Physical Meeting Minutes Template;

2.2.3 Internal Communication

PROBONO is a collaborative project between 47 partners from different countries and areas of expertise. The Consortium internal communication strategy aims at ensuring the appropriate transparency and cooperation among partners, as well as the timely generation, collection and storage of project information in the Project Space. The strategy includes three main methods of communication:

1. email exchanges,
2. face-to-face meetings, and
3. web meetings (teleconferences).

2.2.3.1 Project Mailing lists

Day-to-day communication is based on e-mails. To facilitate rapid e-mailing and ensure the correct inclusion of involved persons, appropriate mailing lists will be created, as shown in *Table 4*.

List Name	Address	Members
Admin	admin@probonoH2020.eu	Partners administrative and financial contacts
General	general@probonoH2020.eu	All project participants, both technical and administrative
PST	pst@probonoH2020.eu	All Project Steering Team Members
WP n , where $n = 1, \dots, 10$	wpn@probonoH2020.eu	All WP n participants
LL m , where $m = 1, \dots, 6$	llm@probonoH2020.eu	All LL m participants

Table 4: PROBONO mailing lists

In addition to these, an e-mail alias will be set up to facilitate communication with the Management Team of the coordinating partner. The address info@probonoH2020.eu will be used for any external communication and support requests related to the project.

The mailing list will be set up and maintained by the Coordinator or WP8 leader. It is the responsibility of each Partner to actively and timely inform the people in *Table 4* on changes of contact details or additional persons involved.

2.2.3.2 Project Communication Tools

In order to improve communication and ease the collaboration among project partners, frequent teleconferences are held at a Task, WP, intra-WP and Project level. For these teleconferences, there is no centrally deployed tool by the Project. The meeting hosts of the respective teleconferences shall use their own available tools and bridges, also ensuring that the meeting links will be shared with the project partners.

2.2.4 Communication Material

The communication material and visual identity of the project have been established in WP8 (D8.15 (M6)) and they will support the implementation of dissemination and communication activities (participation in events, workshops, conferences etc.) aiming to contribute to the overall perception of the project and its uniform impression. The communication material includes elements that will represent the project in a distinct and consistent way (logos, colours, fonts, templates, photos, etc.). All material and information used by the project partners for dissemination and communication purposes, including publications, must include the following sentence as acknowledgment:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101037075”.

2.2.5 Amendments to the Grant Agreement

Over the course of this project, circumstances might arise to call for a request to the EU for an amendment of the GA. Various reasons could cause the request for a GA Amendment, such as a change of partners, change of legal entity, changes affecting the project or its implementation, changes involving the financial aspects of the grant and changes in the DoA. In case an amendment is needed, the Project Steering Team (PST) will be the formal decision-making body for the issue. To initiate the amendment procedure, the Project coordinator will have to submit such a request after an autonomous decision by all partners in the PST. After approval, the Coordinator will distribute the revised Grant Agreement to the partners, thus replacing the former version of the Grant Agreement.

2.3 Report Oriented Deliverable's Quality Procedures

2.3.1 Quality Criteria

Last minute's proofreading is not sufficient. Rather, we need to ensure from the beginning that the content planned for the Deliverable will cover everything that is required. As already mentioned above, Annex I presents the scoring template that needs to be completed during the peer review process, which provides more specific criteria according to which reviewers should evaluate each document type Deliverable. The need for specific quality criteria comes from the need for a standardized way of screening outputs and the benefit of a uniform result towards a unique quality outcome. Therefore, it is defined early enough and notified to the authors of reports what are the key criteria the documents will be judged against so that delays are avoided and quality is enhanced in a 'by-design' notion from the very beginning. The scoring sheets for the peer reviewers is another tool to be used to provide the author with feedback on how well the report was prepared and how it can be improved. These criteria are also summarized in *Table 5* below.

Quality Criteria	
Quality of Content	Main objective of the Deliverable is fulfilled and addressed
	References are appropriate and complete
	Methodology is appropriately justified
	Results are useful and valuable to the project and comply to DoA
	Conclusions are justified, well based, relevant and applicable. The conclusion chapter reflects all described main important issues in the report
	There is no plagiarism and previous work or work of others is clearly identified as such (this will be checked only by the QAM with a specific tool)
Readability	The document is easy to read
	There are no obvious spelling or grammar mistakes
Structure	The document is consistent with the Description of Work (DoW). The reader can easily tell (e.g., by looking at the ToC) where in the document each point of the DoW is addressed
	The document structure is logical, appropriate and easy to follow
Conformance to the Template	The document template has been applied properly
	Figures, graphics and tables are legible, readable and referred in the document's text
	The Document length is less than 100 pages. There might be an exception in case where many figures are included in the document
	References (papers and other sources) are correctly cited and referenced
	All mathematical symbols are properly defined

Table 5: Report Oriented Deliverables – Quality Criteria

2.3.2 Quality Procedures

In order to ensure the successful results of the QA procedures, the following actions are required:

2.3.2.1 Progress Monitoring and Reporting

The progress monitoring process will be performed on a monthly basis in alignment with WP Leaders reporting process via teleconference between the WP Leaders, QM and the Coordinator. Apart from reporting on the status of each Task, WP Leaders will also be responsible for reporting on the status of the Deliverables under their WP in order to identify possible issues or delays on an early stage. In addition, each partner should report effort and expenditures every three months.

On a WP level, each WP Leader is responsible for monitoring of the Tasks and the work that has been done, or will be done by the Task Leaders. It is up to each WP Leader to set up this Task monitoring process under his/her WP.

2.3.2.2 Quality Assurance and Peer Reviews

In order to ensure the deliverables are submitted on time according to plan and they are of high quality the following scheme as in *Figure 3* will be adapted throughout the lifespan of the PROBONO project. Let M_i denote the i^{th} month at which a specific task initiates, while M_s denotes the s^{th} month at which the deliverable under this task is submitted. Then we define 3 additional status checkpoints between M_i and M_s as follows

- The ToC must be decided (between the author (TL), the WPL, and the contributing partners) and be ready by the end of M_{i+1} (i.e., 1 month after the task initiation);
- At M_{s-2} (i.e., 2 months before submission) the deliverable must be at 50% (i.e., most of the content and figures and tables to be present);
- At M_{s-1} (i.e., 1 month before submission) the deliverable must be at 100% ready (i.e., all of the content and figures and tables to be present together with formatting).

Figure 3: Deliverable progress until its submission

The quality procedures will have five steps as shown *Figure 4* while all the stages of the QA process are described in detail in *Table 6*.

Figure 4: Report-Oriented Deliverables – QA Procedures Diagram 1

The following figure shows how the deliverables will be handled once they are at 100%, i.e., at M_{s-1} :

Figure 5: Report-Oriented Deliverables - QA Procedures Diagram 2

From the above figure, one can see that the following responsibilities are in place:

- **Lead Author (LA):** Setup the Deliverable ToC, collect and consolidate contributions, prepare the final version, report issues and delays to **WPL**. The lead author also sends the final version of the deliverable directly to the QM.
- **Contributors:** Provide quality input on-time, and respect timelines.
- **WPL:** Monitor the Deliverable progress but also the relevant Task (in a monthly basis), report issues and delays issues and delays to the **PC** and **QM**
- **QA Manager:** Act as “auditor” and perform quality check on each checkpoint, ensuring quality and on-time delivery. The QM sends the final deliverable to the Peer Reviewers (**NOT the authors themselves**).
- **Peer Reviewers (PR):** Perform review check 1 month before submission to ensure the comply to DoA.
- **Coordinator (PC):** Performs the last check and modifications (if needed), and submits the Deliverable.

QA Stages & Procedures		Description	Relevant document
Stage 1: Checking the planned content	1 Month after Task started (M_{i+1})	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Author has the Deliverable ToC ready ▪ This should be agreed with Task participants & WP Leader 	
Stage 2: Checking the actual content	4 Months before the submission (M_{s-4})	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Author should initiate Deliverable writing ▪ Author should ask for contributions from Task participants 	Deliverable template
	2 Months before the submission (M_{s-2})	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Author should have the Deliverable ready by 50% ▪ Contributions from Task participants should also be in the 50% 	
	1 Month before the submission (M_{s-1})	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Author should have the Deliverable ready by 100% (content & formatting) ▪ Quality manager sends the Deliverable to the 2 Peer Reviewers (for a 1-week review) 	
Stage 3: Final adjustments	Submission Month (M_s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Peer Reviewers provide their feedback (within 1 week) ▪ Author provides the final Deliverable version (ask additional contribution from partners if needed) ready for submission (within 2 weeks) 	Peer Review Plan
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Final check by QA Manager & quick scan by the Project Coordinator (ACC) ▪ The Project Coordinator (ACC) submits the deliverable. 	Scoring Table

Table 6: Report-Oriented Deliverables - QA Procedures & Stages

The proposed review timeline, and the relevant deadlines will serve as a common baseline for all deliverables where applicable. *Practically however, where some tasks have started but will need research/investigation time before commencing the next deliverable milestone (e.g., ToC, or 50% input), the task leader will communicate the timeline adjustment needed to Quality Manager, Work Package Leader, and peer reviewers, to best serve the output of the task at hand.*

Example: Table 7 shows an example of the Quality Assurance deadlines and checkpoints for Deliverable D8.15 “Project visual identity”. The related Task (T8.1) started at M1 (01/01/2022) and the Deliverable needs to be submitted at M6 (30/06/2022).

Task		Deadline	
	Start Task	M1 ($i = 1$)	31/01/2021
M_{i+1}	Outline and ToC ready	M2 ($i = 1$)	28/02/2021
M_{s-4}	Initiate Deliverable Writing	M2 ($s = 6$)	28/02/2021
M_{s-2}	50% Deliverable	M4 ($s = 6$)	30/04/2021
M_{s-1}	100% Deliverable + Peer & QM Reviews	M5 ($s = 6$)	31/05/2021
M_s	Final adjustments + QM/Coordinator Review + Final Submission	M6 ($s = 6$)	30/06/2021

Table 7: Quality Procedures Example

As it can be seen from the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) [2] workflow diagram in Figure 6 below, under the responsibility of the Quality Manager there are two QA checkpoints to ensure the quality of the Deliverable and its timely submission. Additional checkpoints are also set (by the Peer Reviewers and the Coordinator) during the last 2 months before the Deliverable is finally submitted.

Figure 6: BPMN Report Oriented Deliverable QA Process

Peer reviewers are the partners who will be responsible for reviewing the Deliverable one month before the final submission to the EC. The Partners will be asked to name the individual people within their organization that will act as peer reviewers. It was identified that the peer review process will be handled by 2 peer reviewers for each Deliverable and it needs to be completed 1 month before the final submission of the Deliverable. The 2 Peer Reviewers of each Deliverable were chosen members from the WP they belong to (to have understanding and effort) but not the task (otherwise they would have been authors) so as not to have conflicts. Mathematical care was taken to not have overlaps of more than 2 concurrent reviews or parallel with writing for the same partner in the same month (where possible). The number of reviews per partner was also made proportional to partner effort. Authors and contributors of each deliverable are excluded from its peer review process, as well as Work Package Leaders, Task Leaders, the PC (apart from a subset of important technical deliverables) and the QAM.

The list of the peer reviewers per Deliverable along with the deadlines can be found in Annex II of the current document. As presented in Table 8 below, there is a balanced number of Deliverable reviews per partner, based on their role in the Project.

#	Partner	Role	Total Peer Reviews	#	Partner	Role	Total Peer Reviews
1	ACC	Coordinator, Project Manager & WP10L	11	25	VIAS	Participant	6
2	INLE	Technical and Innovation Coordinator & WP7L	5	26	USC	Participant	6
3	FRHF	WP4L	9	27	BLABS	Participant	8
4	SERCO	WP1L	1	28	STAM	Participant	10
5	MM	GBN Expert	6	29	DCN	Participant	5
6	AU	Participant	6	30	MAD	Participant	6
7	AKKA	Ethics and Data Protection Officer & WP5L	7	31	SOP	Participant	6
8	ITA	Beneficiary	6	32	COWI	Participant	7
9	GECO	WP2L	6	33	ACE	Participant	0
10	UCD	Participant	6	34	VISB	Participant	7
11	DLR	Participant	8	35	CELSA	Participant	6
12	IRTSX	Participant	8	36	CIDAUT	Participant	10
13	RESAL	Participant	6	37	TSRV	Participant	9
14	KNT	Participant	6	38	IDOM	Participant	0
15	VLTN	Participant	6	39	SONAE	Participant	6
16	EBOS	QAM	1	40	WT	Participant	6

17	TUC	WP3L	8	41	ECOF	Participant	6
18	TPF	Participant	10	42	ANE	Participant	8
19	IBPC	Participant	6	43	BEE	Participant	6
20	SIN	WP8L	4	44	CAPW	Participant	8
21	DIN	Participant	4	45	CGBC	Participant	6
22	CARTIF	WP6L	8	46	CTU	Participant	6
23	PNO	WP9L	6	47	PRAGUE	Participant	5
24	EUR	Participant	7				

Table 8: Number of total peer reviews per partner

In addition, the Peer Review Scoring Template (Annex I) document defines quality standards for reports to be completed as part of the peer review process. It is available in SharePoint under the “WP10” folder.

Completed scoring sheets and comments on the document to be completed as part of the peer review process should be sent to the Quality Manager and uploaded to the SharePoint under the appropriate Deliverable Folder (i.e., Files > Deliverables > WPn). Along with the scoring document, the Peer Reviewer can make corrections inline the Deliverable document (using track changes) but also add comments where he/she believe is necessary. The Deliverable document (with changes and comments) should also be sent to the QM, as part of the peer review process.

2.3.2.3 Issue Reporting and Escalation

On each Quality Assurance stage mentioned above in *Table 6* “Report Oriented Deliverables - QA Procedures & Stages”:

- Both author and the WP Leader are responsible to provide a high-quality Deliverable.
- Quality Manager will perform a quality check based on the quality criteria (*Table 10*).
- Quality Manager will report the QA results to the coordinator.
- Delayed and low-quality Deliverables will be reported as “under-performance”.

All issues need to be reported immediately by the Deliverable owner or the WP leader to the Quality Manager. The multiple checkpoints allow the Quality Manager to identify (in early stages) potential problems (technical, business or other) and bottlenecks that might affect the timely submission of a Deliverable and the project in general.

In case an issue is identified or reported (during the stages of the QA), the following mitigation actions and corrective mechanisms need to be followed:

- The Quality Manager immediately contacts both the Deliverable owner and WP leader in order to discuss the issue and find a quick solution avoiding any delay on the Deliverable.
- In case the issue cannot be solved, then the Quality Manager contacts the Coordinator and informs her/him about the situation. All parties will discuss the issue trying to find a suitable solution.
- In case a decision cannot be taken, and the issue persists, the Coordinator needs to contact the Project Officer and inform him about the situation.

Everything reported in this Section is also applied in the Software-Oriented Deliverables (Subsection 2.4 of the existing document).

2.3.2.4 Milestone’s monitoring

Parts of the report-oriented Deliverables are also the Milestones, as identified on the DoA. Milestones are directly correlated to one or a set of Deliverables and Tasks. The QA procedures and monitoring will be performed through the procedures for report-oriented Deliverables that have already been described. The successful completion of the Milestones is very important for the project’s success. The milestones, including their due dates, are listed in *Table 9* below.

MS#	Name	WP	Due Date	Means of verification
1	MS1	1, 7, 8, 10	M9	Set up project identity, operating procedures, and strategy tools optimisation
2	MS2	1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 10	M12	LL Vision/KPI Formalisation and evaluation/monitoring procedures/tools established
3	MS3	1 – 7, 9, 10	M18	LL social/behavioural engagement and innovation plans in place; User Acceptance Scenarios established
4	MS4	1, 3 – 8, 10	M24	Baseline KPI metrics calculated, and LL procedures finalised with stakeholders; DT and design tools optimised for LL's. Monitoring and evaluation framework complete
5	MS5	1, 2, 3, 8, 10	M30	LL Designs finalised, energy systems planned, and construction plans initiated for LL's
6	MS6	1, 3 – 10	M36	Interim progress and monitoring report on LL Construction, behavioural and innovation strategies first release; First releases of smart GB construction and energy monitoring platform and DT models
7	MS7	1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8	M42	Operation and performance monitoring of LL's begins, Initial Capacity building completed
8	MS8	1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10	M48	Framework complete. Interim monitoring report on LLs progress and innovation Optimisation
9	MS9	2 – 7	M54	Second Interim Monitoring Report. The innovation developments are complete and finalised. Final innovation optimisations; The Living Labs evaluation finishes;
10	MS10	2, 3, 6 – 10	M60	Final project output collation. Exploitation and LL evaluation; peaks in Capacity Building and Exploitation; Final reporting

Table 9: Project Milestones

2.4 Guidelines for Software Oriented Deliverables Quality Procedures

2.4.1 Quality Criteria

Similarly, to report generated outputs, the quality criteria's aim in software-oriented output is to ensure that technically-oriented Deliverables are of a sufficient quality. It is beyond the scope of this quality plan however to enforce software (or hardware) development practices since responsible partners are experts in their fields

and the ones to decide on relevance and appropriateness. It is the partners' duty to select the most suitable practices and approaches based on the requirements of their tasks.

The PROBONO partners will be in close collaboration with the technical team of the project in order to decide the final detailed considerations and procedural control points that will be designed at the early stages once an iterative and solidly defined framework is decided upon to ensure convergence to the technical objectives in alignment with technical actors. The scope of this report is to study and surface the best practices from experience which can benefit work ahead and guarantee quality results on time and as per scope.

For the software-oriented outputs, we define a checkpoint at $M_{(s-4)}$ (i.e., 4 months before submission), when full documentation of all functional specifications should be completed. The technical team, which includes the relevant WP and Task leader, will ensure adherence to requirements. Some preliminary key criteria have been identified to be investigated and decided upon by the technical and quality team:

Quality Criteria		
Software quality	Acceptance tests are consistent with the DoA and overall project plan.	
	Acceptance tests are consistent with the expected use of software.	
	Test results have been signed off.	
	Prototype is functional.	
	Real or realistic test data usage.	
Accompanying document (usually a report with explanations)	Content Quality	Main objective of the Deliverable is fulfilled and addressed.
		References are appropriate and complete.
		Methodology is appropriately justified.
		Results are useful and valuable to the project and comply to DoA.
		Conclusions are justified.
		No Plagiarism.
		No syntax or grammatical mistakes.
		Main objective of the Deliverable is fulfilled and addressed.
	Readability	The document is easy to read.
		Appropriate and common-used fonts are used.
	Structure	Easy visualise where key points are addressed.
		Easy identify WP Tasks as described to DoA
		The document structure is logical and appropriate.
	Follow the Template.	Template has been properly applied.
		Figures, graphics, statistic and screenshots are legible and clearly readable.
		Document length is less than 100 pages. There might be an exception in case where a lot of figures are included in the document.
		References and papers are correctly pointed.
		Template has been properly applied.

Table 10: Quality Criteria for software related outputs

Note:

1. The above criteria are by no means exhaustive. Further factors will be included pending technical discussions that will take place as the project progresses to ensure robustness and timely completion.
2. Both the software module to be produced and the accompanying report describing it should also be reviewed and validated by the technical coordinator, quality manager and project coordinator.

2.4.2 Software-oriented outputs elements

In a similar way to report-oriented deliverables, quality procedures and plans are also to be established for the software-oriented deliverables to ensure quality and that proactive measures are taken to mitigate risks, which could jeopardise the project planned outcomes. The purpose is the delivered software to cover the tasks and LLS' needs and be fully aligned with the project's plan objectives.

To ensure the quality of the technical output itself, a list of key elements has been studied and identified towards achieving the requirements targets. These elements are available to the teams' toolkit and will be investigated further once a more solidly defined framework of infrastructure emerges across the work packages and the needed technical objectives are set.

- **Quality Reviews**

As described below and under the responsibility of the Technical team (WP and Task leaders), multiple QA checkpoints are established to guarantee the high technical outputs' quality and on-time submission.

If any issues, during the stages of the QA, are identified by the Quality Manager or reported by the Task leader or any other partner, then the mitigation actions and corrective mechanisms described elsewhere in the document must be followed in order to avoid any unexpected delays on the submission.

The PROBONO project aims to produce different kinds of software modules, which will be eventually utilised by the LLS. The quality procedures for software-oriented deliverables, as described above, correspond to the life cycle of each software module and can be applied during its development. The life cycle of each software module could consist of:

- **Software requirements and business modelling document**

The requirements document must be written by the LLS along with the technical partners. In this document, all the business information about the use cases will be recorded as well as the information and the data that needs to be handled. It also defines which of the recorded information are related and important for the business, in what part of the process are being generated, where are going to be used and who will process them.

- **Software specifications and data modelling document**

This document describes in detail the specifications of the required software solution and provides a clear picture of what data objects need to be available, their attributes, the relationship between them, and also the structure of the messages that need to be exchanged.

- **Software design and process modelling document**

This document defines the flow of data as required by the business model, between the data objects, where it is being created and used. It also defines the flow of the messages that need to be exchanged.

- **Software coding and application generation**

In all cases, automated tools are used to facilitate the software construction and development. Modules are created to be reused and objects can be easily integrated.

- **Software testing**

This process is continually conducted (informally) by the technical partner who is responsible for the application development and coding during the entire development lifecycle. Testing is also performed formally at the end of the prototype development in conjunction with the LLS use cases end users who will provide evaluation metrics and realistic "real life data". For consistency UAT forms or other could be used to document any

requirements that are yet to be addressed or were addressed unsatisfactorily.

- **Software integration**

This process is conducted according to the in-house procedures of the main partner responsible for technical integration.

- **Software integration testing**

This process is conducted by the main partner responsible for technical integration in a formal manner at the end of integration.

3 Conclusions

This document describes the work that has been performed in T10.3 “Quality Assurance” during the first twelve months of the project. This includes the quality plan, the criteria, the rules and the procedures that need to be followed in the PROBONO Project during the different stages of the Deliverable preparation and writing. Mitigation actions that are taken in case an issue has been identified or reported, are also described in the document. Furthermore, the current document describes the actions and processes to monitor the Quality Assurance, ensuring that the project Deliverables meet the defined quality standards, while conforming to the security requirements.

The document also defines the peer reviewers for each Deliverable (Annex II). Peer reviewers for each Deliverable were selected in an independent and appropriate way, based on each partners’ expertise and participation in the Tasks, while the effort of the reviewing process has been spread proportionally to all of the project partners.

The main aim of the QA plan is to assist, support and guide partners who are responsible for the output of the project to achieve its targets. The plan is by no means a one-off exercise and will be enforced in many stages of the project to make sure it reflects developments, or even address arising risks coming from the internal or external environment. Finally, communication to all consortium remains crucial to the quality assurance aim, therefore, apart from assigning clear responsibilities, the task will reinforce open, clear and frequent communication with all partners.

4 References

- [1] M. Goddard, "The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): European Regulation that has a Global Impact", *International Journal of Market Research*, vol. 59, no. 6, pp. 703-705, 2017. Available: 10.2501/ijmr-2017-050 [Accessed 10 February 2021].
- [2] R. Dijkman, M. Dumas and C. Ouyang, "Semantics and analysis of business process models in BPMN", *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 1281-1294, 2008. Available: 10.1016/j.infsof.2008.02.006 [Accessed 10 February 2021].
- [3] Boehm, B.W., "Software Risk Management: Principles and Practices," IEEE Software, January 1991, pp.32-42.
- [4] Williams, A. Laurie, "An Introduction to Software Engineering" Williams Publishing, 1st ed., August 2014, ISBN 978-0989864015

Annex I: Peer Review Scoring Template

PROBONO Peer Review Sheet for Deliverables							
Deliverable Number						Score Values	
Deliverable Name						OK, perhaps some minor comments	●
Version						Is of reasonable quality, needs some re-work	●
Review result						Needs substantial rework or additional work	●
Deliverable Author	Name	Organisation	Email	Phone			
Reviewer							
Content							
#	Criteria	Explanation	Score	Explanation of Score by Reviewer	Suggested improvements	Response from Author/Writer	
1	Main objective of the deliverable	Does it set out to do what it says in DOW? Are objectives clearly and simply stated and in line with the Description of Work (description of the Task). Further is it clear how these objectives are relevant to the overall targeted results of the project as a whole.					
2	References and building on previous work	Have they overlooked any state of the art, previous work, related projects, regulations or best practices Does the report include and make use of relevant and necessary references?					
3	Methodology	Was the work, development, trial, experiment or study conducted in a sensible way? Are the Methods/procedures appropriate and correct?					
4	Conformance of Results	Did the deliverable do what was promised? Is the aim of the deliverable achieved? Do the findings and results of the work match the objectives as described in the Description of Work and are these results clearly described in the deliverable.					
5	Usefulness of results	Is the deliverable (and associated results) actually useful to downstream tasks or customers. Is it clear that the results are useful and relevant? Is it clear how results can be accessed Are plans realistic and actionable? Is it clear that they are not committing downstream tasks to something impossible. For example KPI targets which cannot be reached or measured.					
6	Conclusion	Is there a conclusion chapter and does it make sense? The conclusion chapter reflects all described main important issues in the report. The conclusions are well based, relevant and applicable.					
7	Plagiarism	There is no plagiarism and previous work or work of others is clearly identified as such.					
Presentation, Structure and readability							
#	Criteria	Explanation	Score	Explanation of Score by Reviewer	Suggested improvements	Response from Author/Writer	
Readability							
8	Readability	Can you understand it easily? Is the document easy to read and understandable.					
9	Language	Are there any obvious spelling or grammar mistakes? Is the English in the deliverable good? Is the writing style clear, concise and accessible?					
Structure							
10	Consistency with Description of work	Can the reader easily tell (e.g. by looking at the table of contents) where in the document each point in the DOW is addressed? Is it clear that the deliverable reflects the description of work?					
11	Structure	Is the structure of the deliverable logical and easy to follow? If you feel it is not, please suggest changes to the structure to make it more accessible.					
Conformance to template							
12	Template	Is the document template properly applied?					
13	Graphics	Are figures and tables legible and referred to in the text?					
14	Length	Is deliverable less than 100 pages in total?					
15	Referencing	Are the papers and other sources correctly cited and referenced? Are terms defined in the glossary?					
16	Terms	Unusual technical terms and acronyms should be added to the glossary. Ideally they should also be defined in text the first time they are used unless this reduces readability or they are well known.					
17	Nomenclature	Are mathematical symbols defined?					
Overall conclusion							
#	Criteria	Explanation	Score	Explanation of Score by Reviewer	Suggested improvements	Response from Author/Writer	
18	Quality	Green - The deliverable can be submitted as is but could be improved if the issues raised are addressed. Amber - The issues raised must be addressed before submission. Red - There are substantive issues with the deliverable they need to be addressed and it will require a second review.					
Any other remarks/comments							

Annex II: Peer Reviewers per Deliverable for Year 1¹

Del#	Title	ToC	50%	100%	Due	Sub Date	Auth	Peer 1	Peer 2
10.1	Project Management Handbook and Yearly Management Reports	Aug-21	Oct-21	Nov-22	M12	Dec-22	ACC	EBOS	INLE
7.1A	Overall LL Implementation Plan and management (I)	May-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	M9	Sep-22	INLE	VISB	ACC
8.15	Project Visual Identity	May-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	M9	Sep-22	SIN	IRTSX	CGBC
10.11	Data Management Plan and GDPR Compliancy (I)	May-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	M9	Sep-22	AKKA	DCN	CGBC
1.1A	GBN Analysis Tools and Decision Support System (I)	Feb-22	Apr-22	May-22	M6	Jun-22	AU	MAD	IRTSX
1.3A	GBN Strategic Vision and KPI Formalisation (I)	Feb-22	Apr-22	May-22	M6	Jun-22	FRHF	EUR	TPF
7.1B	Overall LL Implementation Plan and management (I)	May-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	M9	Sep-22	INLE	VISB	ACC
1.7A	GBN Transition Challenges, Enablers & Future Roadmap (I)	May-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	M9	Sep-22	RESAL	MM	TPF
1.5	GBN Scenario Generation Strategic Case Studies	Oct-22	Dec-22	Jan-23	M14	Feb-23	TUC	CIDAUT	FRHF
1.10	GBN Integration Strategies and Transition Models (I)	Aug-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	M12	Dec-22	SERCO	IBPC	CGBC
2.1	Stakeholder mapping and analysis	Oct-22	Dec-22	Jan-23	M14	Feb-23	SIN	ANE	EUR
2.2	Behavioural analysis and operational best practice	Aug-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	M12	Dec-22	EUR	VISB	CELSA
3.1	SOTA Reports and DT Models (I)	Aug-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	M12	Dec-22	TUC	BLABS	ANE
3.16	Knowledge Graphs and Agent-Based Modelling (I)	Aug-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	M12	Dec-22	TUC	STAM	COWI
6.1	PROBONO Evaluation Framework	Aug-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	M12	Dec-22	CARTIF	CAPW	ACC
8.1	Dissemination and communication strategy & reporting (I)	Aug-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	M12	Dec-22	SIN	SERCO	CARTIF
8.5	PROBONO Alliance Liaison (I)	Aug-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	M12	Dec-22	SIN	FRHF	UCD
10.6	Quality Plan and Monitoring (I)	Aug-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	M12	Dec-22	EBOS	AU	DLR

¹ Deliverables in highlighted in red typeface have requested extension from the PO and the final delivery date has been modified from the contractual date as in the GA. The dates presented in these deliverables are the new final dates.

Annex III: Deliverable Template

Deliverable n°:	03.1
Deliverable name:	Name
Version:	1.0
Release date:	dd/02/2022
Dissemination level:	xxxx (Public, Confidential)
Status:	xxxx (Draft, Peer-reviewed, Submitted, Approved)
Author:	SIN – Salima Ismayilzoda

It is necessary to include background for the work reported in the deliverable, reasons for choosing a solution, discussion among possible solutions before choosing one, relation to other project deliverables, tasks, and WPs (inputs used, outputs created), as well as concrete conclusions of the documents.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101037075. This output reflects only the author's view, and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
0.1	dd/mm/2022	First draft version	Salima Ismayilzoda

Contributors:

Partner	Contributor
SIN	Salima Ismayilzoda

Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer

Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task

DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhood (GBN) aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green building is a **green building** that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green buildings are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhood (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and **collaboration**, that ensures just transition that **improves** the economic and social **conditions**, considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (DGNB) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a **transparent** framework for the construction operations, conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

¹ Please refer to the last updated reports for the latest status of the definitions.
² <https://www.ecoibc.org/what-is-green-building>
³ <https://ec.europa.eu/euro-ndp/>
⁴ <https://www.ecoibc.org/what-is-green-building>
⁵ <https://www.ecoibc.org/what-is-green-building>
⁶ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/943 & Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001
⁷ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001/2001

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Life cycle assessment (LCA)¹ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)² is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)³ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/registry/detail?publicationId=2014-0316-11e8-cc79-000118781212&language=en>
² <http://www.sfnepd.nl/starting-to-think-about-life-cycle-approaches/161614>
³ <https://www.enr.com/resources/management/life-cycle-costing>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY 8

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 1.1.1 Subsection 10

2. CONCLUSION 11

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Table of figures

FIGURE 1: CAPTION 9

List of tables

TABLE 1: CAPTION 9

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PROBONO Grant agreement n° 101037075

Abbreviations and Acronyms

List of abbreviations only related to this deliverable.

Please complete the following proposed one, deleting the unnecessary items.

Acronym	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PMC	Project Management Committee
PO	Project Officer
PS	Project Secretariat
QM	Quality Management
SC	Scientific Coordinator
TMT	Technical Management Team
TL	Task Leader
	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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PROBONO Grant agreement n° 101037075

Executive summary

Include basic/brief information about the document, its scope and relations with other deliverables, summary of related work done, and main findings/conclusions

Deliverable - Name Page 8 of 13

PROBONO Grant agreement nº 101037075

1. Chapter

Normal text

- Bullet 1
 - Bullet 2
 - Bullet 3

Note¹⁰

1. Numbered list

Figure 1: Caption

Table	

Table 1: Caption

¹⁰ footnote

Deliverable Q₆₆- Name Page 9 of 12

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1.1 Section

Normal text

1.1.1 Subsection

Normal text

1.1.1.1 Subsubsection

Normal text

Division

Normal text

Deliverable Q₆₆- Name Page 10 of 12

PROBONO Grant agreement nº 101037075

2. Conclusion

Include the main conclusions that summarize findings, lessons learnt and next steps.

Deliverable Q₆₆- Name Page 11 of 12

PROBONO Grant agreement nº 101037075

References

Example. (2014). Example - Granofers.

PROBONO Project . (2021). PROPOSAL_101037075-PROBONO-H2020-4C-GD-2020-7-PART_B_Section_1.

Annexes

Deliverable Q₆₆- Name Page 12 of 12

Annex IV: Presentation Template

The Integrator-centric approach for realizing innovative energy efficient buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods

Number and title of WP

Name of Leader
Company
Kick off Meeting, Madrid
Date

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PROBONO

Agenda

WP#

- Click to add text

PROBONO

WP#

Main Objective

- To provide value-oriented analysis tools for GBN
 - To define the GBN Integration Strategies
 - To....
- Max 5, please start with the main one, then list only those for the first reporting period (next 16 months)!

WP #

List of Deliverables

- To provide value-oriented analysis tools for GBN
 - To define the GBN Integration Strategies
 - To....
- Please indicate the total number of Deliverables, then list only those for the first reporting period (next 16 months)!
- Please indicate the number of Deliverable, Title and Date of Delivery!
- Who is in charge and who is taking part in!

WP #

List of interlinks with WP7 LLs

- Output to WP7, for ex. process definition to/for...
- Input needed from WP7 related, for ex. LLab constrains for technology/process development
- Please indicate the most important ones, you can divide them by Phases of LLab (design, construction, implementation, monitoring)

WP #

List of interlinks with WP1-6 ? If any.

- Inputs needed from WP1-6, for ex. process definition to/for ...
- Please indicate the most important ones and be focused to the first reporting period (next 16 months).

WP #

List of interlinks with WP1-6 ? If any.

Text

- Text

- Text

Text

- Click to add text

PROBONO

WP #

Thank you!

Name of the presenter

Company

Email

Phone Number

PROBONO

Annex IV: Telco/ Physical Meeting Minutes Template

The integrated approach for making smarter energy efficient buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods

Meeting:	TCC meeting, M2
Date:	dd/mm/2022
Location:	
Version:	1.0
Release date:	dd/02/2022
Dissemination Level:	Internal
Author:	SIN – Salima Ismayilzoda

Minutes

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PROBONO Grant agreement n° 101037075

DEFINITIONS*

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life¹. Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhood aligned with the European Green Deal², is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a geographically defined area that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and approaches to flourish e.g., climatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)³ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁴ and Renewable Energy Communities⁵ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhood (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and appropriate infrastructure that ensures just transition that includes the economic and social governance, considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and well-being.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a common framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

* Please refer to the list submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions.
¹ <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-is-a-green-building>
² <https://ec.europa.eu/easip/en/what-is-a-green-neighborhood>
³ <https://ec.europa.eu/easip/en/what-is-a-green-neighborhood>
⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/easip/en/what-is-a-green-neighborhood>
⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/easip/en/what-is-a-green-neighborhood>

Meeting name - Minutes

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Life cycle assessment (LCA)¹ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)² is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)³ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/easip/en/what-is-a-green-neighborhood>
² <https://www.life-cycle-assessment.org/starting-to-build-a-life-cycle-assessment>
³ <https://www.life-cycle-assessment.org/starting-to-build-a-life-cycle-assessment>

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3.1 Section

Normal text

3.1.1 Subsection

Normal text

3.1.1.1 Subsection

Normal text

Division

Normal text

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4 AOB

5 To Do

No.	Action	Responsible	Due date
1			
2			

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